

Eastern England SDE Airlock Manager Statistical Disclosure Control Standard Operating Procedure

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Purpose

This document describes the complete procedure followed by airlock managers when reviewing researcher outputs prior to egress from the Eastern England Secure Data Environment (EE-SDE).

The purpose is to ensure that all outputs leaving the secure environment considered “safe outputs” with low disclosure risk. This SOP also ensures they are assessed in a consistent and auditable manner, and that Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) principles are applied appropriately before release.

This document combines both governance and operational detail. It explains:

- How airlock managers access and retrieve outputs
- How outputs are assessed for disclosure risk
- The distinction between ACRO-assisted and non-ACRO outputs
- How decisions are made and documented
- When and how escalation occurs
- How audit records are maintained

The technical infrastructure described reflects the EE-SDE egress implementation. Other Trusted Research Environments (TREs) may operate different infrastructure and should adapt the operational sections accordingly while retaining the governance and decision-making structure described here.

Roles and Responsibilities

Researcher

The researcher is responsible for generating analytical outputs within the secure environment and submitting them for egress through the EE-SDE’s Data Transfer and Review Component (DTRC). The researcher must provide:

- A clear description of the output
- The intended use of the output
- A brief rationale explaining how the output aligns with the approved project scope and analytical objectives, as defined in the Data Access Request (DAR) and approved analytical plan
- Where applicable, evidence that ACRO has been used

The researcher remains responsible for ensuring that the outputs submitted reflect only the approved analyses.

Airlock manager (Primary Reviewer)

The airlock manager is responsible for conducting the disclosure review. This includes:

- Accessing the secure environment and retrieving the output
- Verifying that submitted outputs align with the approved project scope by referring to the Data Access Request (DAR) and associated documentation
- Applying Statistical Disclosure Control principles
- Assessing secondary disclosure risk
- Recording a clear, justified decision
- Initiating escalation where required

The airlock manager is empowered to approve or reject outputs where the disclosure risk is clear and precedent exists.

Second airlock manager (Independent Reviewer)

Every decision must be subject to independent confirmation by a second airlock manager.

The second reviewer must:

- Independently review the output
- Confirm that SDC has been appropriately applied
- Confirm agreement with the decision and justification

This “Four-Eyes” principle is a core governance safeguard.

Data Management Team

The Data Management Team (Lead) acts as the first escalation point in cases where:

- Disclosure risk is unclear
- The case is borderline
- Airlock managers are unsure/disagree
- The output falls outside established precedent

The Data Management Team provides structured assessment and advice on the further action that needs to be taken.

DAC Chair

Where required, the DAC Chair provides final governance determination, particularly in cases involving novel risk scenarios or outputs beyond previously approved conditions.

SDC during the Egress Process

In the EE-SDE, the airlock manager uses SDC principles during the output review stage, after a researcher submits an egress request and before any approval is granted for release.

The application of SDC principles at this stage is to ensure that no released output enables:

- Direct identification of an individual and attribute disclosure about an identifiable individual or small group
- Secondary disclosure through combination with other released outputs or public information

This applies irrespective of whether or not the researcher used ACRO. ACRO provides structured checks and metadata; however, it does not replace the airlock manager’s responsibility to make an auditable disclosure decision, including secondary and contextual risk. At the end of this process, every output must have a disclosure control decision associated with it. Every request must be recorded as one of the following:

Decision	Description
Yes	Safe to release in its current form
No	Not safe to release
Yes, but...	Safe to release only if specific mitigations are applied

For decisions recorded as “**Yes, but...**”, explicit conditions must be defined (e.g., aggregate X to level Y, remove stratified Z, suppress cells below threshold, remove outlier points).

Approval decisions must consider both disclosure risk and alignment with the approved project scope. The process to reach this decision is described below.

Output Checker Decision Flow

Figure 1: This Flowchart gives a start to end visual map of the output checking process.

SDC Checklist

This checklist is intended to be operational and usable by airlock managers with basic SDC familiarity. Please refer to the comprehensive guide provided below.

Tabular outputs (tables, counts, breakdowns)

1. Primary Disclosure
 - Confirm there are no small cells below the agreed threshold (or that suppression/aggregation has been applied appropriately)
 - Check for dominance (where one individual or unit contributes most of a value)
2. Class Disclosure
 - Check for class disclosure risk, ensure that individuals in small or homogeneous groups cannot have sensitive characteristic inferred, even if their identity is not directly revealed
 - Example: If a table shows that 5 patients in a small village aged 90+ have Condition X, then even though no names are given, it becomes possible to infer that any known 90+ resident in that village has that condition
3. Review the level of stratification: Excessive segmentation (e.g., age × sex × geography × rare condition) can increase the overall disclosure risk, even when each individual table appears non-disclosive
4. Ensure totals and subtotals do not leak suppressed values.
 - Example: If a table shows:
 - Total patients in Region A = 100 and males = 97 and females = suppressed. Even though the female count is hidden, it can be easily calculated, it creates small-number disclosure risk

Visual outputs (plots, charts, figures)

1. Check whether outliers are effectively identifiable (especially where small subgroups exist)
2. Check whether rare categories are singled out by labels, annotations, or unusually sparse points
3. Ensure charts do not embed raw values that create small-number disclosure
4. Check that axis labels and category labels are not overly granular or identifying (e.g., single year ages, rare diagnoses, small geographies)

Narrative outputs (text summaries)

1. Check that text does not describe unique cases, rare combinations, or identifiable events
2. Confirm language remains aggregated and does not allow “jigsaw identification” when combined with public context

Secondary disclosure

Consider previous releases from the same project: is this output adding detail that makes earlier releases re-identifiable

Note:

Where risk is present, the decision should normally move to “Yes, but...” (with required mitigations) or “No”, unless escalation provides an agreed exception path.

Please refer to the SDC Handbook for more comprehensive guide.

<https://securedatagroup.org/guides-and-resources/sdc-handbook/>

Alignment with Approved Project Scope

In addition to assessing disclosure risk, the airlock manager must ensure that all outputs are consistent with the approved project scope and analytical objectives.

This should be verified by referring to the Data Access Request (DAR) and any associated project documentation.

The airlock manager should confirm that:

- The outputs correspond to the approved research question and objectives
- The population, cohort, or subject matter aligns with what was approved
- The level of detail and stratification is consistent with the agreed analysis plan
- No additional or unrelated analyses have been included

If alignment cannot be clearly established, the airlock manager must seek clarification and, where necessary, follow the misalignment handling process before proceeding.

Operational Process: Accessing and Retrieving Outputs in the EE-SDE

This section documents the EE implementation. Other TREs can replace this section with their local equivalent while retaining the governance framework.

Prerequisites:

SDE admin: Fetches storage location details for egress folders.

Airlock manager: Creates storage locations in DTRC

Researcher: Uploads outputs into their allocated egress folder and raises an egress request via DTRC.

Workflow Overview

Step 1 – Request Creation

- When a researcher raises an egress request in DTRC, a service desk ticket is created in the airlock queue
- The service desk ticket issue contains metadata about the request (input payload, file paths, project_id and requester name)
- On creation, the service desk ticket is automatically assigned to the Automation Bot as the reporter. The airlock manager must update the reporter field to reflect the named requester provided in the ticket description

Step 2 – Assessing Outputs

1. The airlock manager starts a Virtual Desktop Interface (VDI) session within the governance project
2. The airlock manager mounts the data associated with the transfer request, as detailed in the service desk ticket
3. The submitted outputs are accessed in a read-only manner and made available for subsequent disclosure assessment

Step 3 – Alignment Verification

Before conducting disclosure checks, the airlock manager must verify alignment with the approved project scope by referring to the Data Access Request (DAR), as described in the section above. This includes confirming that the outputs are within the approved analytical scope and do not contain unexpected variables, populations, or analyses.

Disclosure Checking Methods

Decision outcomes

Every request must be recorded as one of the following:

Decision	Description
Yes	Safe to release in its current form
No	Not safe to release
Yes, but...	Safe to release only if specific mitigations are applied

For decisions recorded as “**Yes, but...**”, explicit conditions must be defined (e.g., aggregate X to level Y, remove stratified Z, suppress cells below threshold, remove outlier points).

Approval decisions must consider both disclosure risk and alignment with the approved project scope.

Note: Expect a README file among the Egressed files, summarising the outputs and providing context for review. Where a README file is not included or where the information provided is insufficient to support disclosure assessment, the airlock manager should request clarification from researcher via the associated service desk ticket

A. Researcher did not use ACRO

1. Researcher directly raises an airlock request.
 - Researcher Narrative: airlock managers can expect that researchers may include a short explanatory note within their airlock request. This note may summarise:
 - The purpose for which the outputs are being egressed (for example, publication, presentation, or further analysis)
 - A short description of the outputs included in the request
 - The researcher’s consideration of potential disclosure risks and mitigation applied
2. Outputs are checked manually against SDC guidance for output checking, the airlock manager should go through the checklist provided above, and if required, refer to this detailed guide with examples <https://securedatagroup.org/guides-and-resources/sdc-handbook/>
3. The airlock manager approves or rejects the request
4. If the output cannot be approved due to potential disclosure risk, ambiguity, or if changes requested are significant, the case must be escalated in accordance with the Escalation Route and Decision Governance section below

B. Researcher used ACRO

1. Researcher raises an airlock request with the finalised outputs generated through ACRO
2. Airlock manager launches the Governance VDI environment
 - i. Mount the researcher’s airlock request
3. The submitted outputs are mounted in a readonly manner. Airlock manager opens SACRO viewer, navigates to the specified folder, SACRO viewer requires the presence of checksum files generated by ACRO to load and validate outputs, without these, ACRO-assisted outputs cannot be reviewed in SACRO viewer. The airlock manager then reviews the output status
 - i. If SACRO status = Pass

- Approve the output for release (subject to any additional governance checks if required)
- ii. If SACRO status = Review
 - Check whether the researcher has provided comments or justification (e.g., exception request)
 - If clarification is sufficient and disclosure risk is acceptable, document the decision and approve
 - If clarification is insufficient, seek further information via the service desk ticket before making a decision
- iii. If SACRO status = Fail
 - Outputs with a “Fail” status should not be approved
 - Notify the researcher via service desk and request re-submission with only approved outputs
- iv. If a submission contains a mixture of Pass and Fail outputs, the egress must not be approved. The researcher is asked to resubmit the request following remediation
 - Note: The EE-SDE treats egress requests as atomic units of review, where all outputs within a request are assessed together to ensure consistency, traceability, and clear auditability. Selectively approving or rejecting individual files within the same request can fragment decision-making across multiple transfers and increase the risk of inconsistent interpretation, particularly when outputs are related or require combined assessment. Therefore, the researcher must be asked to resubmit a new egress request containing only the approved (Pass) outputs
- v. If concerns remain unresolved after clarification
 - Escalate in accordance with the Escalation Route and Decision Governance section below

4. When the request is received, the airlock manager records the approval in the Audit Log with reason “Approved via SACRO”, along with other required information

At this stage, after the output decision has been confirmed, the airlock manager follows the steps here to approve the outputs. And notify the SDE Admin for next steps.

Handling Outputs Not Aligned with Approved Scope

In addition to disclosure risk, outputs must be consistent with the approved project scope. Where outputs are not aligned, the airlock manager must take appropriate action.

Examples of misalignment may include:

- Outputs relating to a different condition, population, or cohort than approved

- Additional analyses not described in the original project scope
- Use of variables, stratifications, or data sources not previously approved
- Outputs or summaries that differ materially from the approved methodology

Action to be taken

Minor issues (e.g., unclear description):

- Request clarification from the researcher via the service desk

Moderate concerns (e.g., unexpected detail or scope expansion):

- Request clarification and supporting justification
- Consider whether mitigation or revision is required before approval

Major misalignment (e.g., different research focus, cohort, or methodology):

- Do not approve the output
- Inform the researcher that the output falls outside the approved scope
- Advise that a DAR update or new approval may be required before egress

Where necessary, escalate in accordance with the escalation process.

The airlock manager is empowered to reject outputs that do not align with the approved project scope, even if disclosure risk appears low.

Escalation Route and Decision Governance

The airlock manager must always aim to make a clear decision where possible; escalation is for rare cases, disagreement, or novel risk.

When escalation is required

Escalation is required when any of the following apply:

- The output does not align with the approved project scope or DAR and requires governance review
- The reviewer cannot confidently determine whether disclosure risk is acceptable
- The output is borderline and could reasonably be argued either way
- The two airlock managers disagree after independent review
- The release request falls outside established precedent or prior DAC conditions
- The researcher requests an exception that may create new risk

Escalation stages

First-level escalation: Data Management Team

The Data Management Team (Lead) is the first escalation point. Escalations must include a clear “case pack” so the decision is efficient and auditable:

- what the output is and why it is needed,
- what the potential disclosure risk is,
- what mitigation have been considered,
- the proposed decision (Yes/No/Yes but...),
- and why the reviewer is uncertain

Second-level escalation: DAC Chair

Escalate to the DAC Chair when:

- the Data Management Team cannot resolve disagreement,
- the case represents a novel risk scenario,
- or the requested release conflicts with DAC conditions or introduces new risk posture

Where DAC Chair input is required, the same case pack should be provided, plus any relevant DAC conditions and project approvals.

The final decision authority rests with the appropriate governance level depending on the escalation stage.

Audit Log

The Audit Log is a central record of all disclosure checking decisions, it ensures that decisions are:

- Consistent – the same type of output is treated the same way across cases
- Transparent – each decision has a reason documented
- Auditable – can be reviewed by other airlock managers and auditors

Format

The Audit Log is maintained in a shared spreadsheet accessible to all airlock managers.

Definitions:

Column	Description
Output ID	Unique identifier for output type
Output Type	Descriptive name (Histogram, Crosstab etc)
File format	Csv, png
Description of Output	Short explanation of what the output represents
Decision	Approved/ Rejected
Reason for decision	Justification
Checked by	Initials of reviewing airlock manager
Reference Service Desk Ticket	Link to Ticket

Use in Practice

When reviewing a new egress request, the airlock manager checks the Audit Log to see if the output type has already been reviewed.

- If approved previously, decision can be recorded consistently (with verification that conditions remain same)
- If new, a decision is recorded with a new Output ID
- The service desk issue description should reference the Audit Log IDs used in the decision

Record-keeping

1. All egress decisions must be traceable to either:
 - SACRO viewer results or
 - Manual SDC review (with reasoning recorded)
2. The Audit Log is the authoritative record for disclosure checking
3. Service desk must include references to relevant audit log entries (as internal note)
4. Permissions to Audit Log are restricted to airlock managers but can be made readable to auditors

Related Documents

- <https://securedatagroup.org/guides-and-resources/sdc-handbook/>

Appendix

Example Audit Trail Entries

The table below provides illustrative examples of how entries should be recorded in the Audit Trail form. These examples demonstrate the level of detail expected when documenting output checking decisions, including both an approved and a rejected output scenario.

Attribute	Description	Example Entry (Approved Output)	Example Entry (Rejected Output)
Sr No.	Sequential identifier for the audit record	1	2

Output ID	Unique identifier assigned to the output submitted for disclosure checking	H001	C001
Project ID	Identifier for the TRE research project associated with the output	A001	A001
Requested By	Username or identifier of the researcher requesting output release	abv	abv
Output Type	Type of analytical output submitted for disclosure review (e.g., histogram, table, model)	Histogram	Crosstab Table
File Format	File format of the submitted output	jpg	csv
Description of Output	Brief description of the content and purpose of the output	Histogram showing age distribution of heart failure cohort (18–65 years)	Crosstab table showing counts of patients by ethnicity and rare disease category
Decision	Final decision taken by the output checker following SDC review	Approved	Rejected
Reason for Decision	Explanation of the decision made during disclosure review	Output contains aggregated distribution with no small cell counts and no identifiable information	Table contains cells with counts below the minimum threshold, creating potential re-identification risk
Checked By	Name or identifier of the output checker who reviewed the output	kn	kn
Reference service desk ticket	Link or reference ID for the associated workflow ticket in the tracking system	ESD-434	ESD-435
Approved Input Payload ID	Identifier of the validated input payload associated with the request	23424df	1212312tsfx

Glossary

Airlock manager – A data security role in Trusted Research Environments, responsible for reviewing and approving data transfers in and out of the TRE.

Audit Log – A centralised record of all output checking decisions. It documents the output type, decision, justification, reviewer details, and associated service desk reference to ensure consistency, transparency, and auditability.

DAC (Data Access Committee) Chair – The governance authority responsible for making final decisions in complex or escalated cases involving disclosure risk or deviations from approved project conditions.

DAR (Data Access Request) – The formal application submitted by a researcher outlining the research objectives, datasets, population, and analytical approach. It defines the approved scope against which outputs must be assessed.

DTRC (Data Transfer and Review Component) – The system used within the EE-SDE to manage data ingress and egress requests, including submission, tracking, and review workflows.

Egress – The process of transferring data or analytical outputs out of the Secure Data Environment following appropriate review and approval.

Four-Eyes Principle – A governance control requiring independent review by a second reviewer to ensure consistency and reduce the risk of error in decision-making.

Jigsaw Identification – A form of disclosure risk where non-identifiable pieces of information are combined (e.g., across outputs or with external data) to reveal identifiable information about an individual or group.

README File – A supporting document provided by the researcher describing the outputs, their purpose, methodology, and any disclosure control measures applied.

SACRO (Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs) – A platform used to review and visualise ACRO outputs, providing a structured interface for airlock managers to assess disclosure risk and document decisions.

Secure Data Environment (SDE) – A controlled computing environment that enables secure access, analysis, and management of sensitive data while preventing unauthorised disclosure.

Stratification – The division of data into subgroups (e.g., by age, sex, geography). Excessive stratification can increase disclosure risk by creating small or unique groups.

Suppression – An SDC technique where sensitive values (e.g., small cell counts) are hidden or removed to prevent disclosure.

Thresholds – Predefined minimum values or limits used in Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) to determine whether an output can be safely released. Commonly applied to counts (e.g. minimum cell size such as ≥ 10), thresholds help prevent identification of individuals by ensuring that groups are sufficiently large and not disclosive.

TRE – Trusted Research Environments, or otherwise Secure Data Environments are highly secure and controlled digital platforms allowing approved researchers access to sensitive, de-identified data for public interest research. These platforms house data and negate the need to move data around.

Virtual Desktop Interface (VDI) – A secure remote desktop environment used by airlock managers to access and review outputs within the Secure Data Environment.